

Some Solutions to Enhance the Role of Thai Nguyen University Students in Identifying and Criticizing Deviant and "Non-Standard" Behaviors in the Current Cyberspace

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ABSTRACT: Students of Thai Nguyen University study and live primarily in the urban area of Thai Nguyen province, Vietnam. They are a young and vibrant force in society, considered the "future of the country." Characterized by their youthful psychology - easy to embrace new things, a desire for freedom, and a yearning for self-affirmation - their understanding of socio-political issues is sometimes limited and flawed. Based on an analysis of some theoretical issues and manifestations of deviant and "non standard" behaviors in the current cyberspace, this article proposes several solutions to enhance the role of Thai Nguyen University students in identifying these deviant and "non standard" behaviors in the cyberspace.

KEYWORDS: Cyberspace, Deviance, Deviant behavior, Students, Thai Nguyen University students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyberspace has become a "special territory" in the information age. While it's virtual, the users are real. Much information is shared with positive intent, but it also contains a significant amount of negative content. Students are a group that frequently uses cyberspace. They are effective users but are also easily misled and deviate from traditional Vietnamese values, ethics, and norms. Cyberspace is a place where misinformation and negative content easily spread among young people.

Thai Nguyen University is a leading center for training, scientific research, and technology transfer in the Northern Midlands and Mountains region of Vietnam. Thai Nguyen University students are always dynamic, creative, and enthusiastic. They constantly study and train to become useful members of society after graduation, contributing to strengthening the nation's high-quality human resources. Each year, Thai Nguyen University enrolls approximately 25,000-30,000 students in its regular undergraduate and college programs. These students come from diverse backgrounds in Northern Vietnam, with a significant number born and raised in difficult rural and mountainous areas. Many are from ethnic minority groups who have limited access to information technology. Moving to the urban area of Thai Nguyen to study in a completely new environment with greater access to the internet and social media has somewhat impacted their studies and lives. Furthermore, these students live far from their families, making it even more difficult for parents to supervise their children's studies and daily lives. This necessitates clarifying its effects in order to identify and explain the positive and negative aspects that social media impacts on the academic performance and lives of students today. Researching the influence of social media on students can help propose valuable recommendations for supporting the education and training of students in particular, and young people in general, in the current era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

For the reasons mentioned above, we believe that "*Some solutions to enhance the role of Thai Nguyen University students in identifying and criticizing deviant and "non standard" behaviors in the current cyberspace*" is a very necessary topic that requires careful research.

II. CONTENT

1. Some theoretical issues

Vietnamese students are a group of young people in society. They are knowledgeable individuals who have access to many new cultures; they are young, healthy, and dynamic; their values are not yet fully formed and are being tested; they experiment with what they have learned from previous generations and absorb from the outside world, etc. They also possess a high degree of

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complexity, encompassing a great diversity in gender, geographical location, value orientations, interests, spirituality, and behavioral patterns, social choices, etc. This segment of the population has considerable power over the socio-economic development of Vietnam. They share common characteristics. Firstly, they have a practical approach, demonstrate in their choice of majors, professions, and knowledge to meet the needs of reality, preparing for future work experience, career orientation after graduation, and a preference for high-paying jobs, etc. In general, their actions are clearly purposeful.

Secondly, Vietnamese students are dynamic. Many students work part-time while studying; they enjoy entrepreneurship; some students even start companies while still attending universities and colleges; they actively participate in volunteer movements;...

Thirdly, young people always tend to expand their relationships, especially peer relationships and group relationships. Teamwork depends on the social environment around us. The changes in students' mental lives in the face of globalization (both the positive and negative aspects of this trend) are strongly leaning towards community spirit.

Fourthly, born and raised in the era of advanced information technology, today's students are distinctly different from previous generations. They have a high level of self-awareness and want to express their individual roles in all aspects and spaces, especially online spaces. There seems to be an emphasis on personal gain over duty, a preference for enjoyment over contribution. Selfless sacrifice for others is less common than before, and if it exists, it's judged more from a pragmatic economic perspective than from a genuine emotional and sharing standpoint. An indifferent attitude towards their surroundings is emerging among a segment of students.

Thai Nguyen University students share many characteristics with Vietnamese students. They constantly strive to learn and acquire knowledge to be well-prepared to serve their homeland after graduation. They study and live in the urban area of Thai Nguyen province, Vietnam – a city with significant cultural exchange and a socio-economic center of the Northern Midlands and Mountains region. Thai Nguyen is a province bordering Hanoi – the capital of Vietnam and the country's economic, political, and cultural center. It is also a province that attracts significant foreign investment, particularly direct investment from global corporations. Therefore, students at Thai Nguyen University possess distinct characteristics:

Firstly, the majority of the university's students come from rural families, many from mountainous areas with difficult economic conditions. Therefore, to varying degrees, they are influenced by their local background during their university studies. Alongside students who are eager to learn and improve, there is also a group of students who are shy and withdrawn, which significantly impacts their job search after graduation.

Secondly, Thai Nguyen University students are friendly, diligent, and sociable, making it easy for them to connect, share, and integrate into new environments. However, they still have insecurities and a lack of confidence in communication, which is a barrier to their job search after graduation.

Thirdly, Thai Nguyen University is located in the mountainous region of Northern Vietnam, and its facilities are not as modern as those of universities in major cities. Furthermore, limitations in the students' awareness lead to less effective and outstanding learning and experiential activities.

Fourthly, the majority of Thai Nguyen University students live far from their families. Their independence is not fully developed, especially without constant family supervision, resulting in excessive social media use by many students, negatively impacting their academic performance and personal development.

Deviant, or "non standard" behavior is a common social phenomenon in social life from ancient times to the present, often existing alongside adherence to norms. According to the Vietnamese dictionary, "deviant" is being skewed, unbalanced, wrong and incorrect [4]. Each group, each community, each society has certain regulations and norms. If each member of that community has behavior that is not in line with the collective, then that is deviant behavior. In other words, deviant behavior is behavior that deviates from the rules and norms of the group, community, or society.

There are a number of causes of deviant, or "non standard" behavior. As society develops, science and technology, especially information technology, develop rapidly with the emergence of numerous modern electronic devices and digital platforms, attracting many users of different ages, primarily the younger generation. Along with this, the way modern families educate their children in the digital age has also changed. Nowadays, young families often give electronic devices to their children to use and remind them on social media applications, which affects the formation and development of each individual's personality, leading to deviant behavior within each family member. In addition, deviant, or "non standard" behavior originates from each individual in modern

society. Many young people have an indifferent, apathetic, or dismissive attitude when encountering norms and values. Along with that, the mentality of wanting to keep up with "hot trends" has spread rapidly on social networks, but these "hot trends" seem to follow no standardized system.

The cyberspace's impact on cultural and ideological life in Vietnam today is reflected in the following aspects: (1) The cyberspace plays an important role in building the national ideology. (2) In the current context, the cyberspace has had a significant impact on how people, especially young people, seek knowledge, think, and perceive life and social activities. (3) The cyberspace is a platform with great effects, contributing to supporting and upgrading, expanding the amount of information to be processed and stored, increasing the speed of processing and exchanging information, and improving access to information resources. However, in Vietnam, the cyberspace always harbors potential risks of undermining state management functions, disrupting organizations and neutralizing essential national security systems and reorienting social consciousness [3].

2. Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors of Thai Nguyen University students in the current cyberspace

Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors on the internet occur in all areas of life such as politics, culture, education, ethics, etc. Every society has certain norms and values, which become important institutions in maintaining order and safety during the development of that society. Therefore, individuals and organizations are required to behave appropriately and correctly, and violating those norms and values constitutes deviation and "non-standard". Depending on the criteria for identification, there are many ways to classify the manifestations of deviation and "non-standard". Typically, distorted viewpoints, ideologies, and thoughts lead to "deviant" behavior in some individuals and organizations. The forms of deviant or "deviant" behavior that deserve condemnation are those that demonstrate incorrect perceptions and actions contrary to social norms.

The youth in general and students in particular are easily susceptible to social deviations, similar to the euphoric state they experience when participating in positive social activities. There are two "deviations" in today's youth that need to be identified and corrected, namely "deviations" in idol worship and "deviations" in morality and lifestyle. "Deviations" in idol worship lead to the phenomenon of young people worshipping and following "anti-standard idols," they don't need to be beautiful, they just need to be unique to become famous by any means, at any cost, without distinguishing between the true and genuine values of human dignity as prescribed by society [5].

The manifestations of deviant and "non-standard" behaviors among Thai Nguyen University students today are mainly in the following aspects:

(1) Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in communication: On the internet, they are people who frequently access the internet and use social networks daily, so their communication language is influenced by "internet language". Some students have a "toxic" attitude towards those around them who are in lower circumstances, or use offensive words to discriminate against others, especially in social network groups. In addition, many students appear on social networks with beautiful words, showing themselves to be well-behaved, polite, and educated, but in reality, they use impolite words in communication and do not distinguish between superiors and subordinates with older people.

(2) Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in lifestyle: Accordingly, some students frequently update their personal status on social media with images that are not true to reality in order to "get likes", "get views", show off their rich and luxurious lives, and display ostentation. From there, these people judge the attitude, feelings, and level of concern of others based on the number of icons of the posts. These things have diminished the true value of life.

(3) Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in learning: According to the author's survey data, 68.2% of Thai Nguyen University students use social networks for 3 hours or more, meaning students spend too much time on social networks, which significantly affects their learning results. Current social media platforms use algorithms to attract too much attention from viewers, wasting time and reducing their concentration on learning. In addition, many students overuse technology, copying materials, not thinking, training their thinking skills, and always considering AI as the most powerful learning support tool.

(4) Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in information reception: Students have been exposed to a lot of bad and toxic information that they themselves could not foresee. The online space is a place where false and negative information is easily spread, so young people can come into contact with inaccurate or harmful content without being able to distinguish it. Many fake news and unverified false information can mislead young people. This can lead to wrong decisions and distorted views about the world. They can easily access negative content such as violence, hate speech, or offensive images. These contents can negatively affect their psychology and behavior, leading to the formation of negative thoughts.

(5) Deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in legal and ethical behavior: Some students have incorrect perceptions when participating in comments on social media pages that affect the reputation, honor, and rights of organizations and individuals, giving themselves the right to speak arbitrarily, promoting the trend of considering human rights higher than sovereignty, blatantly violating ethics and law, upholding their own human rights but disregarding the rights of others. Many student shares violate copyright, insult the honor of others, contain information that is not secure, and are easily used for fraud.

3. Some basic solutions

To enhance the role of Thai Nguyen University students in preventing their deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in the current online space, attention should be paid to the following basic solutions:

Firstly, each Thai Nguyen University student needs to improve their responsibility, select and verify information before sharing. Education on smart and safe social media use should be promoted in schools, helping students make positive changes in using and effectively exploiting social media for learning, researching materials, and other activities. This will give them sufficient awareness to protect themselves from harmful content.

Secondly, there needs to be coordination between families, schools, and society in guiding, adjusting, and instructing young people to distinguish right from wrong, so that they can understand and act in accordance with norms and values. Parents need to pay attention to and supervise their children's internet use, guiding them to access information selectively. Schools need to integrate digital skills education into the curriculum, helping students better understand their rights and responsibilities when participating in cyberspace.

Thirdly, actively promote and raise awareness about receiving accurate information in cyberspace and the consequences of spreading misinformation. The content of the propaganda should include traditional Vietnamese moral norms and values; policies and laws of the Vietnamese State; and development orientations of Thai Nguyen University. The main entities for this propaganda are the Youth Union and the Student Association of Thai Nguyen University. The forms of propaganda need to be innovative, creative, and flexible, tailored to the specific characteristics of students in all departments of the University.

Fourthly, the Vietnamese government needs to strengthen the management and control of content on online platforms, especially social media sites. At the same time, relevant authorities need to impose stricter penalties on acts of exploiting cyberspace to distort facts, defame, and destabilize society.

Fifthly, the press, radio, and television play a crucial role in guiding public opinion, highlighting good examples and exemplary individuals in identifying and criticizing deviant and "non-standard" behaviors. Criticism of wrongdoing in the press should not only describe and reflect uncivilized and substandard incidents and behaviors, but also provide thorough analysis, offering recommendations and guidance to prevent young people from becoming deviant and "non-standard".

III. CONCLUSION

Identifying and criticizing deviant and "non-standard" behaviors in society and on the internet is the responsibility of the entire society, in which students play an important role in creating a healthy and safe online environment and contributing to building a civilized and sustainably developed society. Given their age, experience, and socio-political awareness limitations, it is necessary to clearly show students the manifestations of deviant and "non-standard" behaviors on the internet today, and at the same time, analyze and help them understand their role so that they can develop comprehensive solutions to prevent their own deviant and "non-standard" behaviors on the internet, such as: 1) Each individual needs to enhance their responsibility, select and verify information before sharing; 2) there needs to be coordination between families, schools, and society in guiding, adjusting, and instructing young people; 3) Actively promote and raise awareness about receiving accurate information online and the consequences of spreading misinformation; 4) Strengthen the management and control of content on online platforms, especially social media sites; 5) The role of media organizations.

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